

SURKHANDARYA OASIS IS A PLACE OF HEALING PLACES

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the number of healing places useful for human health in the Surkhan oasis, the role of the main product of this place in our life, the healing spring water "Amonkhona", its composition, the salt mine "Khojaikon", its places and our health scientific-theoretical views about its benefits are described and analyzed.

We all understand that health is the highest happiness. Health and long life have always been the highest dreams of mankind. A person who wants to live a happy and peaceful life must be healthy, both physically and mentally. In this sense, there are different recommendations and directions in different nations regarding the methods and conditions of health care. Folk medicine has been used in the treatment of various diseases since the birth of a community of people. Oriental medicine has not only age-old experiences, but also spiritual and scientific foundations. After gaining independence, our country will rise to the level of global development. Protection and strengthening of citizens' health has risen to the level of the main policy of our government and leadership. After that, the health centers of our country started their activities. One of such places is the Amonkhana pilgrimage site, famous for its spring waters. Before giving information about this shrine, let's think about water, which is its main product. As a result of the researches of the Japanese doctor Emoto, who lived in the 20th century, he proves with undeniable evidence that water has powerful, healing properties. Water is the bridge that connects a person's physical body with his thoughts, intentions, feelings, and psyche. Did you know that the water you drink can improve your health? In nature, we find various types of water products. Some of them are not suitable for consumption. There are healing waters in many regions of our country. Currently, the most useful and healing water is the spring water of Omonkhan, located in Boysun district of Surkhandarya oasis. Surkhan oasis differs from other regions in terms of climate. This oasis attracts a lot of attention from tourists and adventure seekers. Because the entire area of the oasis is of historical importance. There are many historical views about the Amonkhana spring and cave. In ancient times, when the army of Sahibgiron Amir Temur came to this area,

he was exhausted. On top of that, soldiers suddenly get sick. Then they drank from the water of the Amonkhana spring, rested in the coolness of this cave, and returned to their original state. In conclusion, it can be said that this place has served to ensure the health of the population since time immemorial. Omonkhana has a special effect on the human psyche with its beautiful scenery and beauty. It was found that the water of the Omonkhana spring contains silicic acid, iron, aluminum and other trace elements. Experts say that this spring water, rich in vitamins and minerals, has healing properties for the liver and gall bladder of the human body. Omonkhana spring water is better than the modern Hemodez liquid, which is used for washing the internal organs of the body, in terms of usefulness and harmlessness. During the visit, you will also see the Omonkhana cave there. Its height is 3.5 meters, and the total area is 60 square meters. In the cave, the temperature in the cave is 5-6 degrees, and in winter it is 20-22 degrees. Local residents call it "Omonkhana cooler". There are also legends about it, and if it is cool and warm in summer, you should not try to take even a pinch of butter left by the locals. Otherwise, the opening of the cave may suddenly narrow and prevent you from getting out. The people of Amonkhana still follow this tradition of the past. Currently, the Omonkhana shrine has been opened in the area. The Greek philosopher Thales described "Water as the beginning of the living world." An adult's body consists of 78% water. In fact, water collects the spiritual energy of a person. The healthy, clean energy contained in the water has the ability to heal both physical and mental ailments.

Uzbekistan is a unique natural place with healing properties. We all know that salts are one of the important components of the animal and plant organism. Table salt has been used in cooking since ancient times. Various salts are also used in medicine. We often think about the harmful aspects of salt, but we do not think that it has beneficial aspects. Salt is essential for our body because salt is also needed for our blood, tears and secreted skin. "Khojaikon" salt mine is one of the most useful, unusual and interesting places for health. This mine is also located in Sherabad district of Surkhan oasis. It was opened in 1989 and from the outside it looks like a salt mine. There are a total of 5 such salt caves in the CIS countries. The cave walls are uniquely covered with a 1 cm to 3 cm layer of salt. The salt deposits are located in a synclinal fold, where the salt layers are reversed, with white salts at the top and red salts at the bottom.

It was included in the national list of immovable property objects of tangible cultural heritage by the decision No. 846 of October 4, 2019. During the year, the air temperature is 7-27 degrees, the relative humidity is 50-70%, and the atmospheric pressure is kept around 700 mm of mercury. The air contains elements such as magnesium, potassium, iron hydroxide and about 20 other trace elements. Staying in this cave is useful in the treatment of long-lasting allergic diseases of the respiratory tract, acute and chronic bronchitis, asthma, complications of pneumonia, patients with reduced immunity, and skin diseases. Our grandfather Ibn Sina said for nothing that "If there was no dust and smoke in the air, a person would have lived a thousand years." The conclusion is that due to the clean air composition of Khojaikon salt cave and Amonkhona shrine, people are recovering from their illnesses. Nowadays, all diseases are treated with chemical drugs. Many people often want others to heal them, or to do it with the help of some kind of tool, various medicinal products. But they do more harm than good. We have shown healing places in our country only as an example of the Surkhandarya oasis. Such

places can be found in many corners of our country. For example: "Turon" sanatorium (located in Tashkent. It is a treatment center for patients with heart, vascular organs, nervous system, andrological and gynecological diseases), "Chinobad" sanatorium (in Tashkent. Balchikli spa), "Ak-tash" sanatorium (treats diseases of respiratory organs), "Chimyon" sanatorium (located in Fergana. Treats diseases of the nervous system, cardiovascular, musculoskeletal system, gynecological and urological diseases), "Kosonsoy" " sanatorium (in Namangan region. The sanatorium treats musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal and nervous system diseases), "Zomin" sanatorium (Jizzakh region. Treats respiratory and nervous system diseases), "Abu "Ali Ibn Sina" sanatorium (Samarkand region. Diseases of the nervous system, cardiovascular, locomotor organs and skin diseases), "Marvaridi Termiz" sanatorium (for patients with diseases of the locomotor system, cardiological, neurological, gynecological, urological) and many others. There are many sanatoriums. When such natural healing places are available, we can use them to restore our health. It is not for nothing that our country is described as a paradise, a country with a cure for every disease. Because we can find solutions to all diseases from the nature of our country. Every disease has a cure.

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